

THE IMPORTANCE OF MEDICAL EXAMINATIONS FOR YOUNG PEOPLE GETTING MARRIED

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The family is one of the most important links in our society. The health of young families is one of the nation's most important social issues. Health screening of young people who marry before they start a family is the first step toward building strong families. Family is the main link of human life. Medical examination of the bride and groom before marriage ensures the strength of the new family and the well-being of the unborn children. In accordance with the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 25, 2003 "On approval of the regulation on medical examination of married persons", future brides and grooms will undergo a free medical examination. The main goal of medical examination of married persons is to prevent hereditary and reproductive diseases, to create a healthy environment in the family.

Despite the fact that the healthcare system is being reformed in our country, reducing the level of non-communicable chronic diseases among various segments of the population, forming a healthy lifestyle, preventing hereditary diseases, improving the gene pool, analyzing the medical examination of married couples and introducing screening studies are among the main tasks facing medicine. In this regard, it is relevant to study and analyze the process of medical examination of married couples and develop measures to improve the quality and effectiveness of observational healthcare.

The purpose of the study: To determine the theoretical knowledge of young married people in the field of medical examination, as well as to determine the characteristics and problems in the application of norms related to this issue, as well as to search for ways to further improve medical examination

Materials and research methods: The socio-sociological views of the young people who came to undergo a medical examination for marriage at the multidisciplinary central polyclinic of the New Life district of Tashkent, and the work of the doctors and nurses working there. socio-hygienic, mathematical-

statistical and evidence-based medical methods were used to collect anamnesis(100) and fill out a questionnaire

Research results: According to the results of the survey, 55% of the married young people interviewed are women and 45% are men. Considering their socio-demographic origin, the youngest age is 18-20 (35%), 21-30 (50%), middle age is 31-40 (15%).

During medical examinations, 55% of the population did not face any problems, 39% of young people faced problems related to queues, 1% did not have tickets for Endocrinologist and Gynecologist examinations, and the remaining 2% faced various problems.

In the list of pre-marriage medical examinations, 20% suggested deepening genetic examinations and free examination, 19% deepening drug examinations, 3% infertility examination, 2% deepening cardiological and gynecological examinations.

49% said that all is well and no further examination is needed, 1% suggested removing cardiology and rheumatology examinations. 3% believe that no investigation is necessary.

The general incidence rates of those who are getting married in the period 2020-2023 are 15% in 2020, 6% in 2021, 16% in 2022, and 12% in 2023.

Conclusion: Before we begin to consider the legal aspects of the medical examination of married young people, we believe that it is necessary to determine what meaning the legislator uses when applying the term “medical examination”

Medical examination of young people getting married is one of the most important and important things today. Future spouses, first of all, should know about each other's true state of health in order to prevent negative consequences of marriage.

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